

PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

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D1.2 Data Management Plan

Version 1.1

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable

Terminology	

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) for PreMETS project. It has been developed in line with the guidelines in the Horizon Europe DMP template <https://www.openaire.eu/images/Guides/HORIZON EUROPE Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>. The policies define data archiving, preservation, and sharing (i.e. access rights) practices to be adopted. Data will be collected within the WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 of the Project and respective datasets defined in the developed DMP.

1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The main objective of this document is to develop the DMP of the PreMETS project. The DMP outlines the ways in which data are collected, generated and/or processed throughout the lifespan of a research project.

The DMP was prepared using the Argos DMP tool (<https://argos.openaire.eu>) for each Work Package (WP) that requires such a plan. Argos allows researchers to create machine-actionable DMPs and ensure compliance with FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable) data handling. It enables collaboration on the definition of research data management plans in the context of projects or grants and subsequently the persistence, publication and exchange of those through a variety of mechanisms.

PreMETS Data Management Plan, along with the dataset definitions for each WP, is publicly available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20> and is also available as an annex A below. The DMP along with the dataset descriptions defined for each WP will be kept up-to-date over the duration of the project to reflect possible policy changes due to ongoing evolution of project requirements.

ANNEX A: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN INFORMATION

PreMETS Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

Predictive Maintenance is a critical element for the optimization of primary resources used in the economy and on fundamental infrastructure systems (while mitigating climate change also). Currently, both industry, academia and VET trainings lack comprehensive PM curricula. The objectives of PreMETS are to introduce an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM process.

The main objective of the Data Management Plan of the PreMETS project is to outline the ways in which data are collected, generated and/or processed throughout the lifespan of a research project.

Funder

European Commission |
EC

Grant

Erasmus Lump Sum MGA

Researchers

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Organizations

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas

Datasets

Title: WP7 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about communication and dissemination.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in dissemination actions, photos, videos + aggregated dissemination metrics.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical, Images, Videos

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to engagement and impact achievement.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the participants + from social media platforms (including website).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure

- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP3 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about microcredential certification framework

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Learner self-declared data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, numerical

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

To enable a better development of the microcredential system.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

User provided data via online questionnaires/workshops.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Education

Trainers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Other

Handle

- Personally Identifiable Information (PII)

- Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)

- Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Through Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Zenodo Community

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Private data will be closed.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbd

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP Leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP4 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about PreMETS Predictive Manufacturing Platform

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Other

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Tracked learning experience data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Text files
- Numerical

- Other

(i.e. time spent on learning content, performance during online evaluations, relevance of the modelled PM strategies in SCEnAT, performance during Teaching Factories, trainer observations during the workbased learning pilots, issues encountered, platform usage ability, etc)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

To enable the trainers to better help the learners shape their own learning paths and improve the training value.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

PreMETS platform

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Education
- Other

Trainers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

- Personally Identifiable Information (PII)
- Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)
- Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)

- Financial information (such as credit card numbers)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Will be uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

However, sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo Community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At least 2 years.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo may be a good alternative.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

TBD

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security
- Other

TBD

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Other

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP2 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about predictive manufacturing training content development

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in the foresight workshops & their insights / know-how related to raising skills.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Text

- Numerical

- Image

- Video/Audio

- Other

(i.e. time spent on creating content and familiarizing with tools, performance during online evaluations and workshops, adaptation and application of the design-thinking model of the TraCCE (2020) project, selective establishment of working groups, peer review results, content and learning pace adjustments for certifications, performance on VET Certification, performance on Higher Education Certification, trainer observations on train-the-trainers content, issues encountered, etc.)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to establish the learner profiles.

Data will be used to provide certified qualifications.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

- From the participants
- From the researchers

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

The dataset includes sensitive data and personal information

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Perhaps Zenodo

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

- Other

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

- Personal/sensitive data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary

- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Other

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP5 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about work-based learning pilots

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New data coming from:

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of PreMETS' products)

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of PreMETS' products)

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical, Videos, Images

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve the learning content & test the project products.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the participants

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP6 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about monitoring and evaluation

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Structured QA data (self-reported) by project partners, participants and external evaluator

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve project processes/outcomes.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the project partners & external evaluator

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure

- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Powered by

PreMETS Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

Predictive Maintenance is a critical element for the optimization of primary resources used in the economy and on fundamental infrastructure systems (while mitigating climate change also). Currently, both industry, academia and VET trainings lack comprehensive PM curricula. The objectives of PreMETS are to introduce an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM process.

The main objective of the Data Management Plan of the PreMETS project is to outline the ways in which data are collected, generated and/or processed throughout the lifespan of a research project.

Funder

European Commission |
EC

Grant

Erasmus Lump Sum MGA

Researchers

Afroditi Anagnostopoulou (orcid:0000-0001-8292-2663)

Organizations

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas

Datasets

Title: WP7 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about communication and dissemination.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in dissemination actions, photos, videos + aggregated dissemination metrics.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical, Images, Videos

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to engagement and impact achievement.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the participants + from social media platforms (including website).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure

- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP3 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about microcredential certification framework

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Learner self-declared data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, numerical

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

To enable a better development of the microcredential system.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

User provided data via online questionnaires/workshops.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Education

Trainers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Other

Handle

- Personally Identifiable Information (PII)

- Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)

- Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Through Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Zenodo Community

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Private data will be closed.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbd

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP Leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP4 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about PreMETS Predictive Manufacturing Platform

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Other

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Tracked learning experience data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Text files
- Numerical

- Other

(i.e. time spent on learning content, performance during online evaluations, relevance of the modelled PM strategies in SCEnAT, performance during Teaching Factories, trainer observations during the workbased learning pilots, issues encountered, platform usage ability, etc)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

To enable the trainers to better help the learners shape their own learning paths and improve the training value.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

PreMETS platform

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Education
- Other

Trainers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

- Personally Identifiable Information (PII)
- Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)
- Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)

- Financial information (such as credit card numbers)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Will be uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

However, sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo Community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At least 2 years.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo may be a good alternative.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

TBD

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security
- Other

TBD

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Other

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP2 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about predictive manufacturing training content development

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in the foresight workshops & their insights / know-how related to raising skills.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Text

- Numerical

- Image

- Video/Audio

- Other

(i.e. time spent on creating content and familiarizing with tools, performance during online evaluations and workshops, adaptation and application of the design-thinking model of the TraCCE (2020) project, selective establishment of working groups, peer review results, content and learning pace adjustments for certifications, performance on VET Certification, performance on Higher Education Certification, trainer observations on train-the-trainers content, issues encountered, etc.)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to establish the learner profiles.

Data will be used to provide certified qualifications.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

- From the participants
- From the researchers

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

The dataset includes sensitive data and personal information

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Perhaps Zenodo

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

- Other

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the PreMETS project.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

- Personal/sensitive data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary

- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Other

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP5 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about work-based learning pilots

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New data coming from:

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of PreMETS' products)

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of PreMETS' products)

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical, Videos, Images

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve the learning content & test the project products.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the participants

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: WP6 Dataset

Template: Horizon Europe

Dataset about monitoring and evaluation

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Structured QA data (self-reported) by project partners, participants and external evaluator

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text, Numerical

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve project processes/outcomes.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the project partners & external evaluator

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

<https://zenodo.org/communities/premets/?page=1&size=20>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure

- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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